

Scottie

Social connectedness in healthcare

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Abstract:

In this paper we present Scottie, a research and design project in which Media Lab Waag Society explores the role of media ICT in supporting existing social relationships of people who are physically or geographically separated. Media ICT is applied to increase social interaction through social connectedness. The authors use the term social connectedness to describe the experience of being part of a social group. This experience is in normal circumstances reinforced by non-verbal, social-emotional stimuli that in our everyday interactions confirm that we are part of this relationship. We describe the sensibilities of our specific user group (children, aged 10 to 15, who have to stay in a hospital for a longer period of time, and are disconnected from their social circle) and the design challenges we face when mediating social connectedness. The prototype underwent several changes in an iterative design process, in which the users played an important role. The user evaluation identified a potentially promising new target audience, namely elderly people who live in nursing homes and are disconnected from their loved ones.

1. Introduction

The research and design project Scottie is initiated by the Amsterdam based Media Lab Waag Society. The project focuses on the support of social connectedness between people, who share a close or intimate relationship (e.g. parent and child), but are involuntarily physically and geographically separated, for example when children stay in a hospital for a longer period of time. With social connectedness we refer to the experience of belonging and relatedness between people, using awareness system [1, figure.1]. However, we like to add to this idea the fact that - although all communication devices have a role in establishing social connectedness - we feel that non-verbal, implicit, social-emotional stimuli that in normal, daily interactions confirm that you are part of a relationship or social group, need special attention specially when people are involuntary separated from their loved ones. How do you transfer the feeling when a mother almost thoughtlessly pets her child on the head when she's leaving the room, the smell of the family dinner being prepared, sharing the family dinner together, the good vibes you get from just hanging out with your friends, just knowing your brother is in the other room because the door is open, the sound of the key in the front door announcing your father is home?

Target group

The target group are children from 10 to 15 years of age, who are hospitalized for at least a couple of days. Being hospitalized and in an isolated situation means that the relationship with friends and family changes and that the children are cut off from customary daily activities. They are no longer part of their normal routines and deprived from the familiar spontaneous and social interactions. The communication with their social circle now becomes planned and 'intentional' or effortful, due to e.g. visiting hours, the use of media, characteristics of the media used or the availability of infrastructure. However, communication is not only a mean to exchange information but also emotions [2]. It serves an important social and personal need, namely the one to feel connected [3]. Even though recently more and more hospitals give children access to a computer next to their beds, in addition to a telephone, most (mediated) communication is limited to the use of (explicit) verbal or text based expressions and images. Our primary focus therefore will not be telephone or language based messages, nor real time video streaming, as the infrastructure for this is already available for the children. The difference made with the design project Scottie is the focus on the development of other forms of communication, which support the relationship by creating a social presence at a distance and add to (social) wellbeing.

People interact as part of many social groups. For our project we focus on the primary, most close-knit, social circle, consisting of the father and mother, the grandparents, brothers and sisters or that one special friend. Since in a hospital setting the nonverbal communication with your close ones is difficult to established, different actors and different acts could address these needs so people feel socially connected.

Figure.1 Social connectedness (by Thomas Visser and Daan van Bel, 2009)

Related work

Previous work on social connectedness has concentrated on linking people at a distance through media ICT. Huijnen describes this as social presence, a feeling of being together, increased through awareness systems [4]. Biemans notes that social connectedness using a photo sharing application simplifies connecting to friends and family without the need to engage in a phone conversation [5]. Scottie tries to accomplish a social connection by communicating in a nonverbal, implicit and playful way. Scottie aligns with other applications mediating this type of intimacy such as the robot baby seal, *Paro*, used as a therapy to elicit emotional responses in patients of

hospitals and nursing homes, the emotional robot cat *iCat*, which can be used as a game buddy for children or play other roles, and the rabbit *Nabaztag* that personalizes (explicit) communication [6-8]. Many projects have not surpassed the stage of prototyping though, just as MIT's *Huggable*, a bear-shaped communication tool between caregivers and hospitalized child, and the robotic friend *Probo* which is aimed at recognizing emotions of children and can respond in an emotional way through facial expression, speech and gestures [9, 10]. While existing technologies enhance the connection between people in a very explicit manner, but are inadequate when supporting expressions of intimacy [3], *Scottie* aims to elicit affective communication between a group of people in a playful manner stimulating the users to develop their own intimate way of communicating through colour, light and sounds. Previous research indicates that the development of an abstract form of personal language appeals to users [11].

DESIGN CHALLENGES

Starting point for the design of *Scottie* is the mediation of a relationship. From research into tribal designs and popular culture an object shape is derived that can best be described as an abstracted human figure. The abstraction helps to create an affective relationship to *Scottie*, as the object not only serves as a representation of dear ones but also needs to have an appeal in itself (figure 2).

As we intended the communication to be abstract, playful, pleasant and uplifting, it is clear we want to move beyond graphical displays and mobile phone or SMS communication. With that in mind the project team has explored visual, tactile and auditory stimuli. Warmth also seems logical as an abstraction of a relationship, but the temperature of the object could not be changed quickly (enough). The context of hospitals also limited the materials to be used (because of regulations on disinfecting).

In the first prototype of *Scottie*, vibration and colour were the drivers of communication and the main means of mediating presence. The underlying idea was that with colour a personal language could be developed. In the current prototype colour and sounds are its main functionality. As a result of user testing, sounds seemed more obvious and appealing as a way to connect to people through *Scottie*.

METHOD

Prototyping fulfils an important role in Waag Society's creative research and design process, especially when exploring playful interactions in an iterative process [12]. Many tools are available to quickly produce and iterate designs. By quickly materializing concepts, new ideas are generated so concepts get more focused. The *Scottie* project team has access to a fabrication laboratory (Fablab) [13]. Prototypes are: functional demonstrators, paper prototypes or interactive 'black boxes' that illustrate an idea rather than a design. Observing how users respond to prototypes has led to new and improved versions of the ideas and helps us define the use and implementation strategies that need to be developed around a product such as *Scottie*.

User participation

Typically, potential users co-operate with the project team in the development of prototypes. In different stages of the project we used methods such as co-creation, interviews, personas and user scenarios to involve users. Later on in the process we moved towards user testing. The first prototypes have been evaluated with two couples of 'healthy' users, as access to the hospitalized target group was difficult because of ethical issues. These

test served to evaluate the usability aspects of the prototype. In addition we explored new interaction principles with the users. The next step was the introduction of Scottie in a hospital setting in a short-term intervention. The interviews conducted confirmed the appeal of having a representation of their dear ones close to them. Potential uses of Scottie were proposed. Based on user scenarios, the idea of a joint activity, such as making music together, was added to the functionality of Scottie. Using Scottie should be like playing a musical instrument; it can be played by oneself, or with others, and its 'goal' can be different for each user [12].

The final Scottie prototype therefore facilitates two forms of play:

1. Creating light patterns
2. Creating sound patterns

In both forms of play, users can play themselves, creates rhythms for or with a friend or relative and jam together.

User evaluation

In April/May 2010 Waag Society started with the evaluation of the final prototype of Scottie with children (and their parents) and with elderly people. Finding respondents turned out to be difficult and time-consuming as it is hard to anticipate hospitalization. In addition, taking care of an ill child is not only very emotional, but also time consuming. Families of chronically ill children therefore have a hectic life, with not much time to participate in research. Some of the respondents turned out to be too ill to participate. One respondent hesitated to use Scottie at home – due to the open-ended nature of the communication - but wanted to use Scottie again when se was going to be hospitalized. Surprisingly, the test with a senior and his family - his wife and their son – turned out to be promising. The senior, though suffering from dementia, learned to recognize the colour as a signal from his son (“He is thinking of us”), whereas his wife confessed missing the Scottie after the testing period of five weeks, when Scottie had to be handed over to the research group. The family states to have had more contact due to the Scottie interference. Recognizing the need for additional communication seems to be a more important factor than user group characteristics as age or illness.

Waag Society has worked with Technical University Delft (TUD) and Cliniclowns to set up and conduct the user tests. Further research will include an open call on (online) forums and magazines targeting at specific target groups and will include more seniors.

Figure 2 A day in the life of Scottie

4. Conclusion and future work

We have described the design principles of affective computing through Scottie, which enable users to connect and interact by developing their own ways of communication using light, sounds and colour. We have also outlined some of the observations of the usability of Scottie. It seems that the design of Scottie, its shape, the possibilities of nonverbal communication appeals to people. We experienced that testing with the primary target group, namely children who have to stay in the hospital for a longer period of time, encountered practical barriers and ethical issues. However, tests with other target groups show the potential of the communication device. In the months to come we will gather additional quantitative and qualitative research data of the usage within and outside hospital settings. Ultimately, we hope that Scottie adds to the development of innovative, tangible interfaces, playful and personalized communication tools and the possibility of creating an intimate language. In this way Scottie will add to the improvement of social connectedness and (social) wellbeing within the context of health care.

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